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**PREDICTION OF PARTICIPATION IN
PARLIAMENTARY ELECTIONS RESULTS USING
SENTIMENT ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES**

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Abstract

In recent years, the application of machine learning techniques to political forecasting has gained significant attention. This paper explores the use of advanced algorithms in predicting the voter participation in the Egyptian Parliament elections. Leveraging a diverse set of features including historical election data, candidate profiles, socio-economic indicators, and sentiment analysis of social media, our study employs state-of-the-art machine learning models to analyze and forecast election results. Support vector machines, Naïve Bayes, decision Tree, random forests, and Bert neural networks are just a few of the algorithms that are implemented as part of the technique to improve the models' predictive power through preprocessing and feature engineering. To guarantee robustness and generalizability, the models are evaluated on a carefully selected dataset after being trained on past election data. The data about political opinions in the 2020 parliamentary elections before and during the election days. Data were obtained in November 2020 before and during election days, where collected data manually and all the hashtags that were created and covered for that after cleaning and filtering the tweets the data volume was smaller. The results demonstrate how well machine-learning methods capture complex patterns in the political landscape. The prediction models' insights deepen our understanding of the variables affecting election results within the framework of Egyptian politics. The study also explores how algorithmic forecasting might be used to influence political agendas, facilitate informed decision-making, and advance a more transparent electoral process.

Keywords: Egyptian Parliament, Sentiment, Twitter, Elections, Algorithms.

I. Introduction

Elections in Egypt have a profound impact on the nation's political landscape and governance. The Egyptian Parliament serves as a crucial platform for legislative decisions, policy-making, and representing the interests of its citizens. However, accurately predicting election outcomes in such a complex and dynamic political environment poses a formidable challenge. Moreover, conventional methods, including polls and expert opinions, may provide valuable insights, but they often fall short in capturing the intricate interplay of factors that influence voter behavior. Accurate forecasting of election results can provide valuable insights for political campaigns, aid in understanding voter behavior, and inform policymakers about potential electoral trends. In the context of Egypt, where political

decisions have profound implications for the nation's future, the ability to predict election results becomes even more critical.

In the specific context of Egypt, where political dynamics are shaped by a variety of factors, ranging from economic conditions and social issues to regional and international influences via social media articles and various hashtags, the application of machine learning holds great promise. Using various algorithmic techniques, we can delve into the complexities of Egyptian electoral behavior, potentially revealing insights that contribute to a deeper understanding of voter preferences and the underlying factors driving election outcomes. Egypt's parliamentary system plays a pivotal role in shaping the country's legislative landscape and policymaking process. Understanding the potential outcomes of these elections can provide crucial information for political parties, candidates, and policymakers, enabling them to strategize and allocate resources effectively. Furthermore, several studies have delved into electoral prediction using machine-learning algorithms.

Through this study, we hope to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on election prediction using machine learning and provide a valuable tool for political analysts and decision-makers in Egypt.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a literature review, discussing prior work on electoral prediction and machine learning applications in election forecasting. Section 3 outlines the data collection and preprocessing procedures, including the description of the Egyptian Parliament election dataset used in this study. In Section 4, we detail the proposed machine learning model and the algorithmic techniques applied. Section 5 presents the evaluation metrics used to assess the model's performance and reports the experimental results. Finally, Section 6 provides a conclusion and outlines potential future research directions.

2. Literature Review

(Dash et al,2023) and (Chung et al,2023) revealed that, Natural Language Processing (NLP) can be categorized into two main areas: opinion mining and text mining. This technology finds application in various social media platforms, including Facebook and Twitter, where it aids in segregating and analyzing people's opinions and posts. Additionally, sentiment mining is valuable in diverse contexts, such as assessing people's emotions regarding movies, products, songs, and more. It enables the distinction between positive, neutral, and negative reviews, making it beneficial for applications in the stock market, e-commerce websites, song recommendations, and other domains to improve predictions and provide more accurate recommendations.

In recent years, the application of machine learning algorithms (Mendez et al., 2023) in various domains has shown remarkable success, and one area that has gained significant attention is predicting election outcomes (Herm et al., 2023).

(Kellner et al,2010) used a support vector machine (SVM) approach to forecast election results in a European context, achieving impressive accuracy.

(Kim et al,2023) explored the use of deep learning models for election prediction in a different political landscape, demonstrating promising results. However, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work has specifically focused on applying machine-learning techniques to predict Egyptian Parliament election outcomes using Arabic paragraph and sentence.

This paper presents a systematic approach to tackle the task of electoral prediction in Egypt using machine learning algorithms such as Support vector Machine (SVM), Naïve bayes, Random Forest and Decision Tree. We begin by conducting a comprehensive literature review on existing work related to election forecasting and machine learning applications in the political domain. Subsequently, we describe our data collection process, providing details on the Egyptian Parliament election dataset used in this study. Then the study presents the architecture of our proposed machine learning model, encompassing the algorithmic techniques employed, feature engineering, and model selection considerations.

2. Background and Related work

This section of the paper aims to elucidate the pertinent research on opinion mining conducted in various languages, encompassing relevant methodologies, micro-blogging system tasks, and the algorithms employed to accomplish these tasks. The analysis encompasses Arabic language with a focus on predicting the outcomes of forthcoming general elections.

1- Background;

In the following subsections, a demonstration of some frequently used machine learning algorithms is introduced:

a.Support Vector Machine (SVM):

The supervised machine-learning algorithm known as Support Vector Machines (SVMs) is utilized for classification and regression problems. They work especially well when dealing with high-dimensional data or when the data cannot be separated linearly. It is a learning system that uses high-dimensional feature space's hypothesis space. Where the number of samples is lower than the number of dimensions, it is taken into more consideration.

By mapping data points to a space with numerous attributes, SVM can arrange data points into categories. This makes it possible to categorize data points even when those data do not readily fall into linearly separate categories. After identifying separators between the categories, the data are transformed so that the category division can be visualized as a hyper plane(Ahmed et al,2021),(Amenta et al,2019)

b.Naïve Bayes:

Another well-liked machine learning technique that relies on Bayesian probability theory is called Naive Bayes, and it's used most often for classification problems. Naive Bayes is a straightforward but efficient algorithm that has been widely applied in several disciplines, such as text categorization, spam filtering, sentiment analysis, and more.

Bayesian Probability: Bayes' theorem, which connects conditional probabilities of events, is the foundation of Naive Bayes. It aids in estimating the likelihood that a given data point will fall into a particular class based on the observable attributes in the context of classification (Hasri&Debby,2022)

Furthermore, here is a description of how Naive Bayes operates:

- Bayesian Probability: Bayes' theorem, which connects conditional probabilities of events, is the foundation of Naive Bayes. It aids in estimating the likelihood that a given data point will fall into a particular class based on the observable attributes in the context of classification.

- Independence Assumption: The assumption of feature independence is what gives Nave Bayes its name. By assuming that the features used for classification are conditionally independent, the approach makes the computation of probabilities simpler. Although this presumption may not always be true, Naive Bayes can nonetheless function very effectively in practice.

- Training: Naive Bayes estimates the probabilities of each feature given each class during the training phase using the training data. This entails figuring out the likelihood of witnessing each feature for each class as well as the prior probabilities, which represent how frequently each class appears in the training data.

- Types of Different Nave Bayes variants exist, each with a unique set of presumptions regarding the distribution of the data. Typical types include: It is assumed by Gaussian Naive Bayes that the features have a Gaussian (normal) distribution. Multinomial Naive Bayes: This approach assumes that features are counts or frequencies and is frequently used for text classification. Bernoulli Naive Bayes: This method is also used to categorize texts, but it relies on binary features (like the existence or lack of words).

c. Random Forest:

Machine learning applications that require both classification and regression often use the potent ensemble learning method Random Forest. It is a flexible and reliable strategy that integrates the outcomes of various decision trees to enhance performance. Complex data handling, avoiding overfitting, and providing feature importance rankings are all strengths of Random Forest. Here is a description of how Random Forest functions:

- I. *Decision Tree Ensemble*: Random Forest creates a decision tree ensemble (collection). Each tree generates an independent prediction after being trained on a random portion of the training data.
- II. *Voting (Classification) or Averaging (Regression)*: The Random Forest uses a majority vote to integrate different trees' forecasts for classification tasks. The predictions for regression problems are averaged. The aggregate outputs of all the trees form the basis of the Random Forest's ultimate prediction (Xia et al,2022).

d. Decision Tree:

A Decision Tree is a popular classification and regression machine learning algorithm that is straightforward yet effective. Decision trees are a common option for many applications because they are simple to comprehend, analyze, and visualize. Here is a description of how decision tree's function:

- I. *Tree-like structure*: A decision tree's internal nodes stand in for features or attributes, branches for decision rules based on those features or attributes, and leaf nodes for class labels (for classification) or predicted values (for regression).
- II. *Recursive Binary Splitting*: Recursively dividing the data into subsets according to the values of the chosen characteristics is the process of generating a Decision Tree. The algorithm chooses the feature that divides the data into subsets that are as pure as feasible in terms of the target variable at each phase (Costa&Carlos,2022).

2- Related Work:

Sentiment analysis is a computational study focused on understanding how opinions, attitudes, emotions, and viewpoints are expressed in natural language concerning a specific subject. This analytical process has significant implications for service providers, enabling them to swiftly assess the reception of new products and features.

Moreover, there are several studies that, examining these sentiments and patterns can yield valuable insights, aiding in discerning public opinions on elections and government policies.

In (Birmingham&Smeton,2011) the authors conducted sentiment and emotion extraction for major leading party candidates, measuring the proximity of political parties based on the sentiment and emotion data. A smaller distance indicates closer political connections between parties (Huanget al,2013),(Hughes et al,2011) also demonstrated the usefulness of Twitter data in predicting election polls and obtaining valuable insights into public opinions.

Previous research (Dicaro&Grella,2012) has addressed challenges in analyzing political tweets; particularly the impact of sarcasm on classifier accuracy (Chang et al,2012) explored how to handle sarcastic tweets where positive sentiments are followed by negative situations. For in-depth sentence analysis, dependency-parsing tools like Stanford Dependency Parser (Aynalem,2022)(referred to as SDP) have been utilized to extract word relations (Chang et al,2012),(Makkar et al ,2023).

Another important study, (Opeoluwa et al,2023). performed sentiment analysis on tweets discussing the candidates Atiku, Tinubu, and Obi as part of Nigeria's upcoming presidential election in 2023. To assess public opinion towards these candidates, they employed Long-short-term memory (LSTM), peephole STM (PLSTM), and two-stage residual STM (TSRLSTM) as STM models for tweet

classification into positive, neutral, or negative sentiments. A substantial volume of pre-processed tweets, free from irrelevant details, was used in the analysis. The results revealed that TSRLSTM performed remarkably well in individually identifying emotions towards each candidate. These findings hold valuable implications for researchers, political analysts, and policymakers as they shed light on the candidates' public perception and the effectiveness of their campaign strategies. The study highlights the utility of sentiment analysis as a valuable tool for researchers in diverse fields, including political science.

In summary, the literature review highlights the potential of machine learning algorithms to enhance electoral prediction accuracy and understanding. By leveraging the richness of available data and algorithmic techniques, these models offer a valuable tool for political analysis and decision-making. However, it is essential to address the challenges associated with data quality, model interpretability, and generalization to ensure reliable and meaningful predictions in the context of Egyptian Parliament elections.

III- Proposed Machine Learning Model:

In this section, there is a description about a novel method for utilizing machine learning to forecast the results of the parliamentary elections in Egypt. Our approach is built to examine a broad range of pertinent data sources, such as past voting trends, candidate biographies, and sentiment analysis of public dialogue as shown in the following Figure(Fig 1), that describe model steps.

Fig 1: Proposed model Architecture

The first phase in our model is Data collection and processing that make data prepare to apply algorithms and training model. Then Build machine-learning model to classify data using algorithms.

1- Data Collection:

The initial stage in the sentiment analysis process(Chaitanya et al,2022),(Shirodkaret al,2020) (involves data collection. Data can be sourced from a diverse array of platforms, including internet blogs, online forums, online data repositories, and social media Twitter. The data about political opinions in November 2020 parliamentary elections before and during the election days. The data was collected manually where all the hashtags that were created before and during the elections were covered for that after cleaning and filtering the tweets the data volume was smaller.The collected 2600 tweets are prominently significant to the voter participation in the Egyptian Parliament elections.

2- Data Pre-processing:

Pre-processing encompasses the essential tasks of data cleaning and filtering, which, if performed inaccurately, can lead to erroneous data classification. Information collected from platforms like Twitter and other social media networks often contains noise, including misspelled words, slang terms, user-generated abbreviations, and extra white spaces, which can adversely impact the accuracy of sentiment classification approaches. As a result, data cleaning is typically applied to rectify these issues. This cleaning process involves various tasks.

3- Pretraining and processing model:

Pretraining models have emerged as powerful techniques for effectively stratifying and labeling data in various natural language processing tasks, including sentiment analysis. The concept involves training a model on a large dataset containing unlabeled text. These pretrained models can capture intricate linguistic patterns and semantic relationships present in the data, which can be leveraged for downstream tasks like sentiment analysis. Once the model has been pretrained, it can be fine-tuned on a smaller labeled dataset specific to the target task, such as sentiment-labeled data for a particular domain or topic. The Pre-trained model used to start labeling the data is Bert neural network model. Data output was positive/negative/neutral as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Labeled output data

	Tweet	Label	Score	Hashtag
0	الرفض الكامل والامتناع عن المشاركة في الانتخابات	negative	0.915516	قاطع_الانتخابات#
1	خلى عندك كرامة قاطع الانتخابات بجد	negative	0.955961	قاطع_الانتخابات#
2	قاطع قاطع قاطع الانتخابات ابرك و افضل لك والله	negative	0.983876	قاطع_الانتخابات#
3	قاطع قاطع قاطع هذه الانتخابات	negative	0.930733	قاطع_الانتخابات#
4	قاطع قاطع قاطع هذه الانتخابات	negative	0.852654	قاطع_الانتخابات#
5	كنتى فين يا كرتونة لما الشعب عنده كورونا	negative	0.993039429	انزل شارك صوتك امانة#
6	ازاى انزل اشارك وصوتى امانة وانا مش شايف ولا مرشح يستاهل التمثيل لنا	negative	0.947095454	#انزل شارك صوتك امانة
7	انا اخرص ولا أتكلم أبدا في هذه الانتخابات	negative	0.75240308	#انزل شارك صوتك امانة
8	دلوقتي بقى صوتك امانة ولازم ننزل بتاجروا بفقر الناس وقلة حيلتهم	negative	0.868643701	#انزل شارك صوتك امانة
9	احنا لا عايزين نشارك في اي حاجة ولا نبيلة	negative	0.92869854	#انزل شارك صوتك امانة

4- Proposed ML model to classify data:

In the previous studies has been explored the application of classical machine learning algorithms to predict the outcome of parliamentary elections. However, these attempts did not produce satisfactory results, with an accuracy of only about 50%. Moreover, recognizing the need for improvement, There are further steps to hyper parameterize these algorithms, hoping to unlock their full potential for policy prediction.

In addition, despite persistent efforts to optimize the parameters of these classical algorithms in previous studies, the results remained suboptimal. This finding underscores the complexity and uniqueness of the Egyptian political landscape, as traditional models struggle to capture the complex interactions between the diverse factors that influence election outcomes.

Furthermore, the strategy has been adjusted towards more sophisticated and adaptable strategies to overcome this difficulty and push the limits of forecast accuracy. To construct a model that is more reliable and flexible, we created ensemble learning, which harnesses the combined power of several algorithms.

IV- Experimental Results:

The obtained results show that, most tweets expressed a negative view of participating in the Egyptian parliamentary elections. The tweets were evaluated using a set of algorithms such as; SVM, NB, Decision tree and Random forest. The highest accuracy was obtained using BERT to perform sentiment analysis on the set of tweets related to voter participation in the elections. The following Tables (2 & 3) shows the advantage of various techniques and limitations will be providing a comparison between all algorithms and BERT:

Table 1 : comparison between various algorithms

Technique	Advantage	Limitation
SVM	SVMs are strong and adaptable, especially when used with the kernel trick. They perform effectively in circumstances where there are more features than samples.	SVMs can be computationally demanding, especially for large datasets, thus, it is crucial to tune the hyper parameters (such the kernel selection and the C parameter) for the best results.
Naïve Bayes	The computationally effective Nave Bayes algorithm performs well for high-dimensional data. It is capable of handling several features and excels at handling text and categorical data. It does not need a lot of training data and is also rather easy to implement.	The strong independence requirement is the fundamental drawback of Naive Bayes. This presumption may produce less-than-ideal results when features are interdependent. Nave Bayes may also have trouble with unusual events that were not represented in the training data.
Random Forest	The robustness, scalability, and resistance to over fitting of Random Forest allow it to capture complicated relationships in the data and handle enormous numbers of features. In general, it is simple to use, requiring little hyper	It might not be as effective on some jobs as specialized algorithms. It may demand more computing power than individual decision trees and is not necessarily as easy to understand as models with fewer variables, like linear regression.

	parameter modification and produces decent results on a variety of datasets.	
Decision Tree	Decision trees are excellent for explaining the decision-making process since they are simple to understand and allow for the visualization of the results. They can manage multi-class problems as well as numerical and categorical data. Decision trees function effectively for straightforward decision boundaries and are reasonably computationally efficient.	Complex trees produced by decision trees often overfit the training set too quickly, which results in poor generalization to new data. To lessen this, several decision trees are frequently combined using ensemble approaches like Random Forests (described in a previous response).

Table 2. Comparison of various Models

Models	Accuracy	precision	Recall	F1 score
SVM	0.3745	0.3951	0.3934	0.3745
Naive Bayes	0.5781	0.5843	0.5868	0.5781
Decision tree	0.5688	0.5756	0.5741	0.5688
Random Forest	0.5688	0.5772	0.5746	0.5688
Bert	0.9545	0.9403	0.9614	0.9550

The accuracy rate in the Bert model is 95% and it is much higher than other algorithms where Bert excels in accuracy, but also in terms of precision, recall, and even F1-score values. Moreover, an interesting pattern became apparent after the data was analyzed: a sizable part of the tweets about the Egyptian parliamentary elections was critical. This view is consistent with reports from the government that are sanctioned and show decreased voter turnout. In addition, the examination of hashtags, which reveals that hashtags linked to negativity are the most used, further supports the idea that there is a high prevalence of negative sentiment in the tweets as shown in Fig5.

Fig 5: Statistical analysis of hashtags after training.

Furthermore, the relationship between the reported low voter turnout and the unfavorable attitude in tweets raises the possibility of a connection between public sentiment and voter engagement. The prominence of negative emotion on social media platforms may reflect public disappointment or unhappiness, which could result in indifference or a lack of interest in voting.

V. Conclusion:

This paper presented a systematic approach to tackle the task of electoral prediction in Egypt using machine learning algorithms such as Support vector Machine (SVM), Naïve bayes, Random Forest and Decision Tree, but these attempts did not produce satisfactory results, with an accuracy of only about 50%. Moreover, recognizing the need for improvement, There are further steps to hyper parameterize these algorithms, hoping to unlock their full potential for policy prediction. Therefore we used Bert Neural network model to predict voter participation in elections to improve the accuracy of sentiment analysis. On testing data, the results showed that the BERT model achieved the best performance at 95%.

Furthermore, the results have shown that, there were relationship between the reported low voter turnout and the unfavorable attitude in tweets raises the possibility of a connection between public sentiment and voter engagement. The prominence of negative emotion on social media platforms may reflect public disappointment or unhappiness, which could result in indifference or a lack of interest in voting. And it matches reality according to the report of the National Election Authority which announced

that the percentage of voter turnout reaches 28% and this is a weak percentage. Moreover, the dynamic nature of political landscapes necessitates continuous refinement and adaptation of models to remain relevant and accurate.

Generally, as technology continues to evolve, so too will the intersection of machine learning and political science. Future research should explore the scalability of these models to accommodate evolving political landscapes and consider the potential impact of emerging technologies on electoral processes.

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(COVER LETTER)

COVER LETTER

Prediction of Participation in Parliamentary Elections Results using Sentiment Analysis Techniques

In recent years, Political life and election have become one of the most important comments on social media sites. Governments have shown a keen interest in predicting the results of election whether presidential or Parliamentary. The application of machine learning techniques to political forecasting has gained significant attention. This paper explores the use of advanced algorithms in predicting the voter participation in the Egyptian Parliament elections. Leveraging a diverse set of features including historical election data, candidate profiles, socio-economic indicators, and sentiment analysis of social media, our study employs state-of-the-art machine learning models to analyze and forecast election results. Moreover, the support vector machines, Naïve Bayes, decision Tree, random forests, and Bert neural networks are just a few of the algorithms that are implemented as part of the technique to improve the models' predictive power through preprocessing and feature engineering. To guarantee robustness and generalizability, the models evaluated on a carefully selected dataset after being trained on past election data. Data were obtained in November 2020 before and during election days, where collected data manually and all the hashtags that were created and covered for that after cleaning and filtering the tweets the data volume was smaller. Generally, the results demonstrate how well machine-learning methods capture complex patterns in the political landscape. The prediction models' insights deepen our understanding of the variables affecting election results within the framework of Egyptian politics. The study also explores how algorithmic forecasting used to influence political agendas, facilitate informed decision-making, and advance a more transparent electoral process.

Keywords: Egyptian Parliament elections 2020; sentiment analysis; Twitter; machine learning techniques, advanced algorithms.

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